

Voices of Families of Color: Navigating White Spaces in Gifted Education

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Abstract

Even when achievement outcomes are equal, some students of color still do not participate in advanced academic or gifted education programs. To better understand this phenomenon, researchers engaged in a research-practice partnership within the local community to explore the experiences of families of color and assess their needs pertaining to advanced learning opportunities for their children. Data were collected during two family outreach events using a semi-structured interview protocol with focus groups. Focus-group interviews were independently coded and analyzed using thematic analysis. Findings revealed challenges and barriers related to accessing enrichment and advanced academic learning opportunities. Some families discussed their personal experiences of racism, bias, and deficit thinking. Overall, themes illustrated how families of color believed they were perceived by educational practitioners and their desire for a sense of belonging and equitable access to high-quality academic programming for their children.

Keywords: equity, gifted education, traditionally underrepresented populations, families

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“White people typically avoid black space, but Black people are required to navigate the white space as a condition of their existence.”

Anderson, 2015

Given the pervasive over-representation of White students in advanced academic programs across the U.S., gifted education is considered by many to be a white space¹ and a modern form of racial segregation (Barnes, 2022; Wright et al., 2017). White spaces are characterized as those that have an overwhelming number of White people and are notably absent of Black people (Anderson, 2015). White spaces were designed and sustained by White people to normalize systems that advantage themselves while simultaneously pushing down people of color (Embrick & Moore, 2020). This speaks deeper to the racial inequities that have served as an Achilles heel for the field. Gifted education programs that reinforce white spaces make it challenging for families of color with advanced children to gain access to the advanced academic services that they value and need.

Students of color are often overlooked or missing from gifted education programs even after controlling for student achievement (Gentry et al., 2019; Siegle et al., 2018). In fact, discrepancies in representation and achievement rates are evident in primary grades, and when evaluating students in the top quartile in reading, these gaps are apparent as early as kindergarten (Petrilli, 2022). Many researchers have examined issues related to equity in gifted education and have proposed potential remedies such as local norms, universal screening, and earlier exposure to gifted education opportunities (Card & Giuliano, 2016; Peters, Gentry, et al., 2019; Worrell & Dixson, 2022). Yet, scholars continue to document inequities related to identification (Hodges et

¹ The decision to capitalize (or not) the terms White and Black was informed by Anderson (2015) and the guidelines established by the American Psychological Association (APA).

al., 2018; Mun, Hemmler, et al., 2020) and racial differences related to students served in gifted education programs (Grissom & Redding, 2016; Yaluma & Tyner, 2018).

Issues of access to and representation in gifted education programs have often been studied using broad, generalized methods, typically focusing on methods of identification or metrics used to identify inequity (Boedeker et al., 2022; Hodges et al., 2018; Lamb et al., 2019). Scholars have also drawn attention to various contributing factors to gifted education's history of racism and segregation, such as deficit thinking (Ford et al., 2001; Ford et al., 2008), unequal opportunity (Davis et al., 2020; Erwin & Worrell, 2012; Plucker et al., 2015), gifted education policy (Peters, Rambo-Hernandez, et al., 2019), and identification methods (Card & Giuliano, 2016; Lakin, 2016). Though gifted education remains under scrutiny, even to the point of budget cuts and the elimination of gifted programs (e.g., New York), many argue that gifted education provides key educational opportunities and advocate to increase access to gifted education programs (Plucker et al., 2015; Wells, 2020).

The Role of Parental Involvement in Student Success

Parents play a central role in students' academic journeys, and there is a direct link between parental involvement and students' attitudes toward school and their academic achievement (Hertzog et al., 2021; Jolly & Matthews, 2012). Additionally, parental involvement influences other important factors for students of color such as motivation (Isik et al., 2018) and STEM self-efficacy (Dotterer, 2022). This connection between parental involvement and students' achievement holds steady from early childhood and elementary education (Ma et al., 2015) through secondary education (Castro et al., 2015), and the transition into college (Jeynes, 2017). Researchers have also highlighted the importance of parental involvement in the

identification process for gifted education programs (Jolly & Matthews, 2012; McBee, 2006, 2010; Mun et al., 2021).

When students' learning needs are met, students experience a myriad of benefits (e.g., psychological, social, academic, life satisfaction, earnings; Bernstein et al., 2021; Hertzog et al., 2021; Kanaya et al., 2019). Advanced learning opportunities are a crucial component of students' educational experiences. In this study, we focused on advanced learning opportunities through the perspectives of families of color. We defined advanced learning opportunities as educational experiences that accelerate or enrich the student's general education curriculum. These experiences may encompass, for example, gifted programs, advanced academic or advanced placement courses, in or out of school enrichment activities, including competitions, online learning, and after school programs.

Equitable Access for Who? Navigating White Spaces

When trying to examine or address equity issues, common approaches come from a White colonialist perspective that students of color should aspire to participate in programs even when they do not reflect their culture or heritage in curriculum or instruction and even if they are not comfortable learning in predominantly white spaces. To put it plainly, traditional school systems were not designed with students of color in mind (Pasque et al., 2022). As a result, some Black parents have chosen alternative schooling methods for their children, such as homeschooling (Fields-Smith & Williams, 2009). Gifted education is no different as it also tends to overlook culture (Ford & King, 2014; Howard, 2018). Denying access to gifted education and the inability to recognize gifted characteristics in Black students has motivated Black parents to turn to homeschooling (Fields-Smith, 2020). In some cases, students of color opt out of advanced learning opportunities altogether for fear of rejection from a predominately white program or that

they will be viewed as a “cultural traitor” (Jeffries & Silvernail, 2017, p. 74). When it comes to equity work, many of us are quick to make gifted education programs more equitable by identifying more students, yet we rarely interrogate the nature or content of the program and whether it supports the students we aim to serve. In fact, Barnes (2022) posed the following question: If we were to successfully solve the problem of under-identifying students from diverse backgrounds (e.g., low-socioeconomic status, immigrant families, students of color, and twice-exceptionalities), are the gifted education programs in which they would enroll in equitable?

Anderson (2015) reminded us that,

The wider society is still replete with overwhelmingly white neighborhoods, restaurants, schools, universities, workplaces, churches and other associations, courthouses, and cemeteries, a situation that reinforces a normative sensibility in settings in which Black people are typically absent, not expected, or marginalized when present. (p. 10)

And so too, gifted education programs in public schools, enrichment programs outside of schools, and other advanced learning opportunities continue to be overwhelmingly white.

Anderson also contrasted white spaces with black spaces, which are predominated by stereotypes of the ghetto or “where the black people live,” describing the ghetto as an impoverished area that is more prone to crime, drugs, and violence, and a means in which White people have historically and legally sanctioned segregation (Anderson, 2012, p. 8; Anderson, 2015). Wright and colleagues (2017) made the same distinction regarding gifted education as a white space and a present-day form of segregation. Tyson (2011) also concluded that black-white racial segregation was still present in advanced courses and gifted education programs and addressed the impact common practices like pull-out programs have on students’ academic self-perceptions, opportunities, and peer relationships.

When navigating white spaces, people of color often experience exclusion, microaggressions, deficit thinking, and racism. For instance, parents of color have reported feeling unwelcome or excluded in school environments (Allen & White-Smith, 2017), discriminatory treatment by school personnel (Reynolds, 2010; Romero et al., 2015), and experiences with deficit thinking (Bertrand et al., 2018; Romero et al., 2015). Consequently, these experiences can lead many parents of color to disengage and avoid school events (Allen & White-Smith, 2017). Moreover, experiences of discrimination in school environments have prompted the need for parents of color to have conversations about racism with their children (Allen & White-Smith, 2017; Gatwiri & Anderson, 2020; Reynolds, 2010; Romero et al., 2015). Black parents have also reported instances of double consciousness, or the practice of viewing oneself through another's eyes and adjusting one's behaviors to avoid reinforcing potential stereotypes held by the dominant group (Du Bois, 1897). For instance, Black parents were aware that school officials perceived them as hostile or confrontational and explained that the simple act of questioning a White teacher or administrator had been seen as a threat (Allen & White-Smith, 2017; Chapman & Bhopal, 2013). Immigrant parents have echoed these experiences of discrimination and being viewed negatively by school personnel (Adair, 2015).

Communication is also a prominent challenge for families of color. Traditional models of school involvement typically employ methods of communication and participation that favor White and middle-class parents (Posey-Maddox & Haley-Lock, 2020). When parents of color have communicated with their child's teacher, they have reported cases where teachers did not respond (Allen & White-Smith, 2017; Tarasawa & Waggoner, 2015) or engaged in deficit-based communication such as communicating only when something was wrong (Posey-Maddox &

Haley-Lock, 2020). Mun and colleagues (2021) similarly noted communication as a barrier to identification and access to gifted education services.

Critical Race Theory and Whiteness Theory

To better understand the person of color's (i.e., families of color in our study) experiences in white spaces (i.e., gifted education programs), we turned to theories of critical race and whiteness. Scholars continue to debate whether the two theories should be considered separately or together; however, we considered these theories together to avoid contributing to the gap between studies using whiteness theory and critical race theory (Chen, 2017). Although there are notable differences between the two theories, both emphasize the role of white supremacy and share the common goal to attain racial equality (Chen, 2017). These theories were important in helping us to understand the perspectives and experiences shared by the families in our study.

A key assumption of Critical Race Theory (CRT) is that society is racially unequal with systems of oppression in place that disempower people of color (Hylton, 2012). Although originally developed by legal researchers, CRT has been used to examine inequity in educational contexts since the 1990s and should apply the following fundamentals in education research (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018): (a) illuminate the issue that achievement systems based on competition lead to racial inequity in education, (b) evaluate educational policies and practices and their role in racial inequity and perpetuating whiteness as the norm, (c) reject harmful narratives that reinforce the idea that people of color are inferior, (d) examine historical connections between present day inequities in educational contexts and patterns of racial oppression, (e) conduct intersectional analyses to uncover how race interacts with other characteristics (e.g., gender, class, sexuality, linguistic background, citizenship status), and (f)

move beyond simple documentation of disparities by advocating for outcomes that meaningfully repair inequities. CRT recognizes and values the knowledge and experiences of people of color, and many educational researchers have used counternarratives within the CRT framework to elevate the stories of people of color to negate stories belonging to a dominant group (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018).

Whiteness theory posits that whiteness, as a social construct, is understood as normal and centric to American and European societies, but it also asserts the need to acknowledge, expose, and ultimately, resist it (Chen, 2017). Owen (2007) described seven functions of how whiteness operates to reproduce white supremacy. These functions helped us to explain the perspectives and experiences of the families in our study: (a) whiteness characterizes a particular racialized perspective that shapes the White subject's understanding of self and the social world; (b) whiteness defines a specifically racialized social location of structural advantage; (c) whiteness is normalized; (d) whiteness is largely invisible to White people and yet highly visible to people of color; (e) whiteness cannot be understood apart from the violence that produced—and continues to produce—it.

In 2020, Black scholars issued a statement denouncing racism against Black people and pointed to systemic issues still present in gifted education programs (Grantham et al., 2020). Two years later, researchers came together to discuss the complexities of equity issues in gifted education and the challenges related to solving an issue deeply rooted in systemic inequity (Worrell & Dixson, 2022). In response to Peters's (2022a) acknowledgement of white privilege in his article about achieving equity in gifted education, Whiting (2022) stated, "To be more precise, you are not privileged because you are White; you are simply accessing structural entitlements that have historically benefitted White people while disadvantaging others" (p. 132).

Whiting continued his explanation by pointing out that white privilege has allowed White people to fully access their rights, such as access to education. Meanwhile, these same practices (e.g., social, political, economic) have “historically abjured Black and Brown children’s rights to quality education” (Whiting, 2022, p. 132). In the same special issue, Barnes (2022) urged scholars and practitioners to understand that racial disproportionality in gifted education programs is a form of systemic racism. She further cautioned that solving disproportionality does not mean we have achieved equity in gifted education. Similarly, Garces-Bacsal and Elhoweris (2022) emphasized decentering whiteness in gifted education as a crucial step toward addressing equity issues. As educators and researchers in the field of gifted education, we must acknowledge the current and historical role that our field has played in maintaining white spaces that privilege White students’ access to advanced learning opportunities. If we are not willing to “disrupt the rules and norms of gifted education” then these spaces will continue to “cater to White students and families” (Howard, 2018, p. 561).

From over 25 commentaries included in the special issue, Peters (2022b) concluded that researchers agreed in two areas: (a) underrepresentation in gifted education is “unacceptable... and requires action,” and (b) we must shift from identification to appropriately serving students’ learning needs (p. 165). We agree with these conclusions and in this study, we sought to understand this complex issue by considering the overarching question: How do we move equity forward without first considering the voices of the families we serve?

Purpose

Very few studies in gifted education have included the voices or perspectives of traditionally underrepresented families (Mun et al., 2021), and research adopting a more personalized approach to equity and access issues in gifted education is limited. The purpose of

this study was to consider and elevate the voices of families of color, to better understand their experiences and perceived challenges and barriers related to enriched and advanced learning opportunities.

Methodology

Research – Practice Partnership

The significance of this study was the exploration of the experiences of families of color as they related to advanced learning. Different from traditional research models, this study was the beginning of a research-practice partnership (RPP) within the local community (Arviso & Bell, 2019). This RPP was a hybrid place-based, research alliance (Coburn, Penuel, & Geil, 2013). In this case, we aimed to seed a long-term research-practice partnership with a local, non-profit organization called Families of Color Seattle (FOCS) and not engage in research that brought no benefit to the organization itself.

Research-practice partnerships are collaborative efforts between researchers and practitioners to use research to focus on practice-related issues (Henrick et al., 2017). RPPs differ from other research frameworks in that they are long-term, focus on issues of practice, committed to mutualism, use intentional strategies to foster partnership, and produce original analyses (Coburn, Penuel, & Geil, 2013). RPPs have received increased attention as an important research methodology to address equity in educational contexts (see Heller, 2021, for a special issue on research-practice partnerships) and improve school systems (Coburn, Penuel, & Farrell, 2021). As such, this framework is rooted in working with community partners where voices of community members come together with educators to address educational inequities and to offer solutions to existing problems. In essence, the community guides the focus of the partnership

work, and the researchers engage in collaborative, sustained inquiry in support of the partnership work (Arviso & Bell, 2019).

The methodology of co-designing research with community partners does not necessarily require theoretical connections to initiate the partnership. Instead, the RPP methodology focuses on practice—making change that matters for the partner—as opposed to writing results for publication to facilitate growth for academics. Therefore, we did not initially use a theoretical lens as our approach to beginning the research. However, families’ responses, particularly how strong the feeling of belongingness in gifted education programs was not present for them and their reference to gifted education as a white space, spurred our deep dive into critical race and whiteness theories to gain a better understanding of what this research means to others.

Context of the Current Study

This study was funded through a grant from the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation to advance educational opportunities for underserved communities. This grant was awarded through a collaboration between The Robinson Center for Young Scholars at the University of Washington (UWRC) and Families of Color Seattle (FOCS). At the beginning of this RPP, administrators from both partners and researchers met to discuss prominent issues related to advanced learning opportunities in Seattle, Washington, and together, we developed research questions, interview questions, and designed data collection events for families.

Seattle has a population of over 700,000 (U.S. Census Bureau, n.d.), and demographics vary based on different neighborhoods in the city and can still be segregated (Balk, 2021). Families of Color Seattle makes it their mission to connect local families of color through support groups and spaces where families can share their culture, skills, and resources. Their mission also centers around racial justice, advocacy, and education. FOCS serves families of

color all over the city, including children from different school districts, which state law grants each district agency to design and implement gifted education programs. Therefore, families spoke about different identification procedures and services that they had experienced, but as we found, families still shared similar views about participation in advanced learning opportunities.

As part of the RPP framework, our shared research questions were developed specifically in the local context of the greater Seattle area. The goal was to listen to local families of color to improve access to advanced learning opportunities sponsored by the UWRC for the constituents of FOCS. Although not addressed in this paper, the second phase of the RPP included implementing programs that would address the issues outlined by our community partner. Overall, we wanted to (a) understand the reasons why many students of color experienced low rates of enrollment in advanced academic programs, (b) examine aspects of enriched and/or advanced academic programming that better served families of color, and (c) create programs that increased opportunity for and participation of students of color in enriched and/or advanced academic programming. Therefore, the following research questions guided the overall partnership:

1. What have families of color experienced when trying to access enriched and/or advanced academic programming for their children?
2. What are the prominent challenges and/or barriers to accessing enriched and/or advanced academic programming for their children as perceived by families of color?
3. What are the critical needs and wants for enriched and/or advanced academic programming as expressed by families of color?
4. How can the UWRC more aptly meet the needs of families of color served by FOCS?

To address these research questions, the study was carried out in two phases: (a) needs assessment – we sought to understand the experiences of families of color and assess their needs pertaining to advanced learning opportunities for their children, and (b) response to families’ needs – we collaborated with FOCS to design and carry out advanced learning opportunities in response to families’ voiced needs during phase one. Phase one (Research Questions 1–3) is the focus of this paper.

Researcher Reflexivity

“Do the best you can until you know better. Then when you know better, do better.”

Maya Angelou

It is important to acknowledge researcher bias and positionality in qualitative studies. The research-practice partnership (RPP) team consisted of two researchers, a practitioner, and our community partner. The grant was written by the researchers, two White females. At the time of the RPP, one was the Director at UWRC, and the other was a Postdoctoral Scholar at the UWRC. The third member of the team was also a White female who served as the Director of Enrichment Programs at the UWRC. All three members have had training in equity and cultural responsiveness and had interest in increasing the diversity of the student population who accessed advanced learning opportunities at the UWRC. This partnership was strengthened by the collegial relationship between the research team and the Director of FOCS, a woman of color, whose children had attended enrichment classes offered by the UWRC. In the focus group interviews, families verbally noted the whiteness of our research team, and this made their voices ever more powerful. Most importantly, our identities and the intersectionality of our identities as researchers only illuminated the frustration of these families and their desire to see change happen in their local communities, and in the field of gifted education itself.

We also wish to express gratitude to the reviewers of this paper who encouraged “a more colorful” accounting of our findings, and a stronger connection to theories that would amplify the responses of families who participated in our study: mainly Critical Race Theory (CRT) and whiteness theory. Although CRT and the historical context of structural racism were studied by both of us, we were not fully prepared to hear the level of racism experienced by these families. The fact that highly trained school personnel and educators conducted their work with bias and prejudice was alarming and eye-opening for us. This verified exactly what whiteness theory explains – we *were and are* part of the system that continues to make white spaces uncomfortable for people of color. The stories shared by the families in this study were enlightening, and although we learned a great deal through this process, we acknowledge that we are still learning, still striving to do better.

Participants and Procedures

Participants were recruited through advertisements (website, social media) and an email listserv by FOCS. The advertisement included an event invitation, recruitment invitation letter, and a hyperlink to registration for each focus group event. The only inclusion criterion for participation in the study was that families self-identified as parents or guardians of a child of color. Registration was capped at 10 families per event. All participants were 18 years of age or over. As part of the grant funding, FOCS gave participating families a \$50 stipend at each focus group event. To clarify the terminology used in the presentation and discussion of our findings, the term *parent* refers to a single participant (e.g., participant quotes) and *family* refers to something shared by or that applied to the whole family (e.g., outreach events had family involvement).

Data Collection: Focus Group Interviews

Focus groups were designed as family outreach events where participating families were invited to share a meal together and activities (e.g., Mancala) were provided to children while families participated in focus group interviews. Focus groups were conducted in person through two family events, one held in November 2019 and another in December 2019. Each family event lasted approximately two hours of which the focus group lasted approximately one hour of the allotted time for the event. Before participating in the family event, participants were provided a paper copy of the consent form and asked to sign the letter of consent in person. After providing consent, participants were provided with a paper copy of a brief questionnaire that included questions related to participants' demographic information and were asked to return completed questionnaires by the end of the event. Families ate and socialized with other families prior to participating in focus group interviews. At the beginning of each focus group session, researchers obtained verbal consent to audio-record focus group interviews. All focus groups were audio-recorded and transcribed by a professional company.

Eighteen parents participated in the November focus group event (Focus Group 1A and 1B) and nine participated in the December focus group event (Focus Group 2) for a total of 27 focus group participants. The first session in November was split into two groups for the interview. Most of the participants were female (88.9%) with approximately 85% of participants identifying as the mother of a child of color. Focus group participants self-identified as Black/African American (37%), Asian American (22%), Hispanic/Latinx (11%), two or more races (11%), White (7%), other (7%), and American Indian/Alaskan Native (almost 4%). Almost 85% of focus group participants were between the ages of 31 – 45 years. See Tables 1 and 2 for a summary of participants' demographics for each focus group event.

Table 1*Focus Group 1 Participants' Sample Characteristics*

Sample Characteristic	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	16	88.89
Male	2	11.11
Race/Ethnicity		
American Indian/Alaskan Native	1	5.56
Asian	5	27.77
Black/African American	5	27.77
Hispanic/Latinx	2	11.11
Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander	0	0
Two or More Races	3	16.67
White	1	5.56
Other	1	5.56
Age in years		
Under 20	0	0
20 – 25	1	5.56
26 – 30	0	0
31 – 35	4	22.22
36 – 40	6	33.33
41 – 45	6	33.33
46 – 50	0	0
Over 50	1	5.56
Relationship to child		
Mother	16	88.89
Father	2	11.11
Guardian/Caretaker		
Other		
Total Interview Participants	18	
Child's Race		
American Indian/Alaskan Native	1	3.57
Asian	4	14.29
Black/African American	6	21.43
Hispanic/Latinx	0	0
Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander	0	0
Two or More Races	17	60.71
White	0	
Other	0	
Child's Grade Level		
Preschool	1	3.57
K – 2	11	39.29
3 – 5	6	21.43
6 – 8	7	25
9 – 12	3	10.71
Total Children Represented	28	

Note. Focus Group 1 was split in half and facilitated as two smaller groups.

Table 2*Focus Group 2 Participants' Sample Characteristics*

Sample Characteristic	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	8	88.89
Male	1	11.11
Race/Ethnicity		
American Indian/Alaskan Native	0	0
Asian	1	11.11
Black/African American	4	44.45
Hispanic/Latinx	0	0
Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander	0	0
Two or More Races	2	22.22
White	1	11.11
Other	1	11.11
Age in years ¹		
Under 20	0	0
20 – 25	0	0
26 – 30	1	12.5
31 – 35	1	12.5
36 – 40	3	37.5
41 – 45	2	25
46 – 50	1	12.5
Over 50	0	0
Relationship to child		
Mother	8	88.89
Father	1	11.11
Guardian/Caretaker	0	0
Other	0	0
Total Interview Participants	9	
Child's Race		
American Indian/Alaskan Native	0	0
Asian	3	25
Black/African American	7	58.33
Hispanic/Latinx	0	0
Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander	0	0
Two or More Races	2	16.67
White	0	0
Other	0	0
Child's Grade Level ²		
Preschool	1	8.33
K – 2	4	33.34
3 – 5	3	25
6 – 8	3	25
9 – 12	1	8.33
Total Children Represented	12	

Note. ¹Age in years is off by one unit as one participant did not report this information. ²One participant reported their children's race during the interview ($n = 2$), but did not report grade level information; therefore, parents' reports of children's race/ethnicity were used for total children represented.

Semi-Structured Interview Protocol

Researchers collaborated with the director of FOCS and designed a brief semi-structured interview protocol for the focus groups. The interview protocol included questions such as, “Can you share what you know about advanced and enrichment learning opportunities in your child’s school or school district?”, “What do you perceive as barriers or challenges for your child to access advanced learning opportunities offered by their school?”, and “What types of programs/classes would you bring your child to if offered by the UWRC?” The interview protocol used to facilitate focus groups can be found in the Appendix. Due to time constraints, not all questions included in the interview protocol were addressed in focus groups but were used as necessary to facilitate conversational transitions and ensure each of the research questions were addressed.

Data Analysis

Focus groups were guided by semi-structured interview protocols and researchers were mindful of some a priori themes including barriers and challenges to access, knowledge of gifted education programs in their schools, and knowledge of enrichment opportunities in their communities. Interview transcripts were independently coded, using analytic induction (Saldaña, 2014). Coded data were then categorized under overarching themes. For example, the quote “white spaces” was placed into the same category as the quote “white structures” under the theme: Systemic Barriers. Thematic analysis is a qualitative method used to “identify, analyze, and report patterns (themes) within data” (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 79). In some cases where an interview excerpt could be organized under two categories, researchers discussed and categorized the excerpt according to the main point of the quote (e.g., sample participant quote: “Then my kids take the test the first time, and we didn’t even know the location. They said it’s

somewhere, and you have to go to the location. Text them and find the location.”). In this example quote, the main point centered on communication about testing as opposed to issues with the test itself and was ultimately categorized under communication as opposed to testing.

Based on a priori and emergent themes present in interview data, we created coding tables (data displays) that included transcript identification numbers, page and line numbers of excerpts, and quotes for each theme that emerged. Data displays showed salient themes in participants’ voices. Data displays were discussed at weekly research team meetings, and discrepancies were handled by examining data displays to achieve consensus on excerpts that presented differences in coding. Salient themes were determined by the number of times concepts or key ideas were mentioned in excerpts from the transcripts, using keywords-in-context (KWIC). Using KWIC increases trustworthiness and is beneficial when researchers want to support meaningfulness of the data (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2007). Table 3 summarizes some of the major themes, frequencies, and sample quotes.

Working as a research team, collaborating on the coding of the transcripts, and sharing the initial findings with the organization in the research-practice partnership enhanced the trustworthiness of this study. In addition, working with our community partner to co-design follow-up programs based on the findings from the focus-group interviews also contributed to the robustness of the findings.

Table 3*Sample of Major Themes and Frequencies*

Theme	Number of Excerpts	Example Quote
Access to Info	34	“...I felt it was always <u>closed doors</u> or really into – <u>I didn’t understand what was happening</u> . One of the things that another AL [Advanced Learning] student parent told me was to <u>don’t ever share that information</u> with everybody because people either will feel jealous, resentful, or treat you differently...” (1123-1)
Parents’ Wants/Suggestions	34	“... <u>I want them to be in a program that still sees the value in them</u> and their exceptional aptitude and where is it going to go and enjoy that journey with them, so just all that together.” (1123-2)
Racism/Bias/Deficit Thinking/Microaggression	32	“I’m not saying that the program is perfect because <u>there have been African American families in there, and they face double racism because they’re one of the few people in the program</u> .” (1123-2)
Sense of Belonging	27	“If the kids find out and <u>that will help them if they see someone who looks like them, people who look like them</u> , you know what I mean. So, <u>it’s just another way of saying, ‘Mom, I belong there’</u> .” (1205-1)
System Barriers	26	“Then our voices are not heard and that’s why we don’t get the resources, and all that, <u>there are a lot of barriers that have broken us</u> , and I hope change will come in the future.” (1205-1)
Communication	21	“... <u>how can we have these open communications throughout the district</u> , throughout the different levels that impact our kids, but don’t come across as confrontational because I’m a person of color trying to get resources for my kids, or that I’m trying to get something for free in some cases.” (1123-1)

Findings

To address research question one (What have families of color experienced when trying to access enriched and/or advanced academic programming for their children?), we began with a priori themes (i.e., barriers, challenges to access, knowledge related to gifted and enrichment programs in schools and communities) and asked families to share their experiences during focus group events. These shared experiences organically led to addressing the second research question (What are the prominent challenges and/or barriers to accessing enriched and/or advanced academic programming for their children?), and several prominent themes emerged from focus group interviews. When families of color shared their experiences and challenges, the following overarching categories emerged: (a) challenges to access, and (b) systemic issues and barriers. Challenges to access included the following emerging themes: (a) lack of access to information, (b) communication, (c) testing, and (d) logistics and resources. Emerging themes categorized under systemic issues and barriers included: (a) navigating white spaces, (b) experiences of racism, bias, deficit thinking, and microaggressions, and (c) sense of belonging.

Findings for the third research question (What are the critical needs and wants for enriched and/or advanced academic programming as expressed by families of color?), were categorized under What Families of Color Want. Emerging themes included under this category were: (a) support and community, and (b) diversity and representation. Findings related to research question three mirrored the first two research questions in that families reiterated that they wanted support, increased communication, access to information, increased diversity and representation, and wanted logistical and resource barriers removed.

Challenges to Access for Families of Color

Access to Information

Overwhelmingly (mentioned 34 times throughout both focus groups), families reported an overall lack of access to information related to in-school and out of school enrichment and/or advanced learning opportunities for their children. Often, information related to advanced learning opportunities was discussed in terms of gatekeeping. For instance, when discussing experiences related to advanced academic opportunities, one parent shared, "...because from my own experience I knew that we were completely unaware; and so, that's one of the things my son was saying, it's the best kept secret when people come in [to the gifted program]" (Focus Group 1B). Other families shared this sentiment, "...we don't all have access to the same parent information, and it's messed up" (Focus Group 1B), with some families referring to gifted education as, "...closed doors" (Focus Group 1A), and another parent referring to it as intentionally, "secretive" (Focus Group 1B). This theme emerged again during the second focus group when a parent shared that many immigrants, "are not informed; they don't know the resources. Even then they're not good with the computers, and they don't know where to go..." (Focus Group 2). Across both focus groups, families were very clear: "accessing information is probably the most critical thing" (Focus Group 1B).

When families did have access to informational sessions and similar events, they noted those experiences as racist in general, as exemplified by this parent, "we went to like an info session, and oh my god, it was very visibly racist against any person of color" (Focus Group 1A). Families' discussions of these experiences also included materials used or distributed at informational sessions such as, "really racist handouts about Native History" (Focus Group 1A) and "racially biased tests" (Focus Group 1B).

Communication

Another major challenge (mentioned 21 times) to accessing advanced learning opportunities was families feeling a lack of or broken communication from schools. Families addressed communication as a crucial piece contributing to their lack of access, “I think it’s probably the piece, one that breaks down into sending the communication out to the community” (Focus Group 1A). When families did receive communication from their schools regarding gifted education opportunities, they “didn’t know what to do with the stuff” (Focus Group 1B), nor was anyone from the school, “explaining how it would benefit their family and their kids” (Focus Group 1B). In addition to the overall lack of communication, families shared frustration over a sense of resistance to communicate and help. For instance, “nobody really wanted to help me, to give me the information, so I had to really go dig for it, like for gifted” (Focus Group 1A). When communicating with school personnel, families of color shared an “apprehension of engaging with administration” especially when they needed to express their desire for “more challenging opportunities for [their] kids” (Focus Group 1A). Many shared the sentiment of wanting open communication without coming across as, “confrontational because I’m a person of color trying to get resources for my kids, or that I’m trying to get something for free in some cases” (Focus Group 1A). All in all, families described communication as nonexistent or as a tedious process in which they had to navigate.

Testing

Issues surrounding testing were also discussed by families (mentioned nine times separate from communication regarding testing). Many families had an issue with testing kids and using a test score to determine eligibility for and enrollment in advanced learning programs. For example, one parent shared, “...academic[s] [are] like a competitive sport, because it’s like your score is defining you, and I’m so against that, so I would get so annoyed that we’d talk to

her about it, but then her friends compared their scores” (Focus Group 1A); whereas another stated, “there is a test you have to go through, so if you don’t pass this test you can’t be in advanced” (Focus Group 1A). Some families addressed the issue of the amount of testing students go through as well as concerns related to racially biased tests,

...my eldest had, you know, the two maps in the CogAT test; and so, my youngest, because it’s been a span of time, she actually had five tests at the age of five, so they’d increased the redundancy in tests, and the tests are extremely socio and not economic and racially biased tests that I completely don’t agree with. (Focus Group 1B)

Families described assessments used to identify students for advanced learning opportunities as, “racially biased” (Focus Group 1B) or “biased towards white” (Focus Group 2). Other families echoed this frustration with the system and assessments used to access the system,

They make it as isolating; they make it as we’re not smart, and that is what the system is made for; it wasn’t made for us, even the testing wasn’t made for us. So, I feel like the fight has to continue, and if a child is benefitting, you have to remember there are a lot of kids that are left out, and it’s not fair. (Focus Group 2)

Logistics and Resources

Other challenges mentioned by families included transportation, finances, and time. Families referenced the challenges many of them faced as full-time working parents. They pointed out the tedious process that often accompanies gaining access to advanced learning opportunities, “I know it’s there, but it’s like all the work you want me to do to get in [to the gifted program] on top of all the work I already do on a regular basis” (Focus Group 1B).

Another parent shared,

The families that my kids go to school with are all working forty hours or even eighty hours, so they have no time to look for resources. They have no time to go to the community, because they're working hard to make ends meet for their families. (Focus Group 1A)

Families also spoke of the unique challenges related to financial resources. One parent stated, "at the same time, we're not a higher income so that put us at even more of a disadvantage as to how they took us seriously when it came to things that we wanted to advocate for our child" (Focus Group 1A). Families also talked about the high cost of enrichment programs and the disadvantages they faced when having to go through the system for testing as compared to their high-income counterparts who could afford private testing. Many mentioned the need for a sliding scale as most families were caught in the "middle," meaning they made too much to qualify for free/reduced lunch but made too little to feasibly afford quality programs for their children.

Transportation was also cited as one of the "biggest barriers" to advanced learning opportunities (Focus Group 1B). Many of the challenges related to transportation included the driving distance to educational programs or came from working parents, some single-parent households, who did not have the time or the resources to transport their children to programs not offered in their local communities.

Systemic Issues and Barriers for Families of Color

Navigating White Spaces

Families explicitly described systemic barriers (mentioned 26 times across focus group interviews). Through these experiences, families expressed feelings of frustration and exhaustion when trying to navigate and find room for themselves and their children in "white spaces"

(Focus Groups 1A and 1B) or “white structures” (Focus Group 1B) of the American school system. As shared by one parent, “I don’t want [my children] to—it’s not their job to dismantle white supremacy; it’s not their job to penetrate these white spaces and then make themselves somehow [have] to show their worthiness” (Focus Group 1B). Families further explained frustration with a system that assumes their needs:

White people who are in place, who feel like they already know what you need so they’re just going to give this, because this is what you need, and you’re not going to have a conversation with me about what me and my community actually need. (Focus Group 1B)

Families also pointed to broader systemic issues, “unfortunately, not to harp on your race, but like a lot of people who are making laws and actions are Caucasian people, right? So, we’re having to like pull ourselves up just to have you listen to us” (Focus Group 1B). Another parent described achievement in the American school system as, “white-centric, this idea of achievement and needing to prove themselves” (Focus Group 1B).

Additionally, families expressed frustration in trying to understand “the system.” For one parent it took them, “2 ½ years or three years to understand the system and to understand that we are powerless to the general ed, that there is an HCP [Highly Capable Program] or advanced program” (Focus Group 1B). Another parent noted, “right now the environment is not set-up to where children and adults and parents can really flourish without us having to lose our mind and yell at people first” (Focus Group 2). Overall, there was unanimous agreement and shared frustration among families when it came to the challenges of navigating a system not created with their needs in mind.

Experiences of Racism, Bias, Deficit Thinking, and Microaggressions

When trying to access, navigate, and/or question the system, families discussed personal experiences of racism, bias, microaggressions, and deficit thinking. Over 32 quotes illustrated experiences of racism, how families of color believed they were perceived by educational practitioners, their concerns for their children, their desire for a sense of belonging, and equitable access to high quality academic programming for their children.

Families shared examples of educators' deficit thinking of children of color, "I noticed through our districts, the teacher and administration, the ways and how expectations are set for certain students is very different" (Focus Group 1A). Another parent noted, "But somehow the teacher treats [daughter] like she is not [capable]; so, can't you see? Unconsciously, the bias is distinct, and I think clearly in school in the classes, and I feel really frustrated by that" (Focus Group 2). Families also pointed to the identification process, "I feel like identification is a big problem, because most people aren't going to identify kids of color, especially not typical kids of color, as smart" (Focus Group 1B). These experiences were further illustrated by the divergent experiences for families of color based on their race. For example, one Asian American parent shared that, "teachers just assumed that because we're Asian we should know about a gifted program" (Focus Group 1B); whereas, another parent shared, "My twenty-year-old went to the same schools; however, he is mixed, and he got more flak from the teachers in regard to his culture, so I found myself being up at the school more" (Focus Group 2).

Families were alarmingly concerned with and conscious of how they were perceived by educators and administrators. Families used the term "confrontational" when explaining how educational practitioners perceived them when advocating for their children. For example, one parent expressed her desire for open communication with the school district while also expressing not wanting to, "... come across as confrontational, but I think that when you ask too

many questions [and] want too much from [them]... it becomes like, here comes that parent” (Focus Group 1A). Another parent shared her experience as an immigrant when she communicated with her daughter’s teacher,

On one occasion, I had to communicate with one of her teachers last year, and then I extended a greeting out by email. Then the teacher asked my daughter in front of other students: ‘is your mother an English speaker?’ And then my daughter said ‘no,’ and [the teacher was] like, ‘I guess so, because I found some grammatical mistakes in her email.’

(Focus Group 2)

One parent further illuminated these perceptions according to her divergent experiences based on her race, “I can’t really talk about her IQ or anything because I look Asian, and everybody assumes that oh, I must be the type of mom who is pushing her child” (Focus Group 1B).

Families also shared concerns related to how their children were perceived by educators, “I think one of the biggest problems facing children of color, exceptionally smart or otherwise, is being pegged as violent when really they’re just diverse” (Focus Group 1B). Family participants recounted instances where their children were treated differently because of their culture or race. Many of these instances included discipline or differential treatment and expectations compared to their White peers. Families also shared instances of peer-on-peer racism in educational settings. For example, “there have been African American families in there, and they face double racism because they’re one of the few people in the program” (Focus Group 1B). Others shared stories of their children being teased by their peers because of their race or because of their being immigrants (Focus Group 2). Some of these instances led to families pulling their children from a particular school or program, whereas others expressed their reluctance to allow their children

to participate in advanced learning or gifted education programs because, “it's mostly white, and they've encountered that their girls have been kind of racist” (Focus Group 1B).

Moreover, families' concerns over their child's safety and wellbeing overshadowed issues specific to gifted education. In other words, most parental concerns related to gifted education were secondary to general experiences of racism, “what I'm talking about is the culturally relevant crap, because you can't get to that education if you commit suicide because you were called the 'n' word too many times” (Focus Group 1A). Another parent shared, “I haven't even gotten to the exceptionally smart part, because I just tell myself—I just need my kids to be able to not get arrested, to get along in society, and things like that” (Focus Group 1B). The experiences shared by these families, even when asked about their experiences related to gifted education, moved beyond issues specifically related to gifted education. Their experiences uncovered the complexities of a system not built for families of color. Overall, as families shared these experiences and their worries and concerns, they also expressed the importance of and their shared desire for their children to have options, access to high quality gifted education, and to feel a sense of belonging in those spaces.

Sense of Belonging

Despite all the issues surrounding access to gifted education, when families did have access, many spoke of the challenges that came with having access to programs not made for them. As one parent described,

everything is a barrier. The cultural context is the barrier, cultural insensitivity, microaggressions, and racism, and once you're in the program, those are all barriers, because you want to freaking leave. You're like I don't belong here, I'm going to leave.
(Focus Group 1B)

Multiple families questioned whether the environment was good for their children after being expected to go to “great lengths” to get them in the gifted program (Focus Group 1A). Another parent shared a similar concern, “...it’s still a struggle because you want your child—if they can qualify... you want them to go through that experience, but you also don’t want to force them into something that may not even be made for them” (Focus Group 1A). Many families were concerned about their children who qualified for gifted education programs experiencing isolation and being away from their friends. For instance, one parent shared their experience when their daughter had to move to a different school to participate in the gifted education program,

All her friends went to one sixth grade middle school across the parking lot, and then she had to go to another school and adjust there. That was really hard, but she loved her dance class. But the other [neighborhood] kids don’t have as much homework, and it’s just the social aspects where it’s kind of like an isolating experience if you want to feel engaged or whatever. That’s why we really looked into independent schools. (Focus Group 1A)

Families shared an overwhelming number of concerns related to the lack of representation and how that impacted their child’s sense of belonging in gifted education programs. Families noted lack of representation in teaching staff as well as peers in the program. Having a diverse teaching staff was imperative for families; in fact, many referred to a diverse teaching staff as one of the most important characteristics of an educational program. As one parent expressed,

the number one thing is having that race and ethnicity [of the] teacher in the school as a person of color, and that’s one of the reasons why we actually followed the principal

because many of her teachers were of color that were fine to work with. (Focus Group 1A)

Another parent stated,

My fourth grader is qualified for advanced learning. She is in a neighborhood elementary school that I'm really happy with, and she's had teachers of color every year there. This year she's got a Muslim teacher and an Asian/Pacific Island teacher in her split classroom, and I would not touch that to move her anywhere else. (Focus Group 1A)

For families whose children were in schools that lacked diversity, families stressed the important need for a diverse teaching staff, "Because for my Black children, particularly my Black male son, I would like him to see faculty, Black males in particular, and I feel like other communities of children would benefit from seeing African Americans in authority [roles]" (Focus Group 2). The importance of a diverse teaching staff, emphasized by the families in this study, has been emphasized by parents in other studies as well. According to Yull et al. (2014), a diverse school personnel provides families with a sense of camaraderie and provides children with role models that reflect their community.

Diverse peer representation was also important to families. Some families used terms like isolation and loneliness to describe their and their children's experiences and frustrations related to the rezoning of district lines or having to leave their neighborhood school to participate in gifted education programs. Often, families pointed out that their children were moved from schools where they had peers that looked like them to schools where they were the minority or the only one. One parent explained, "after you get the access and you've done all the work to get there, it's like now I have to have another conversation with [child] about being the only one in

here... and it's like welcome to America" (Focus Group 1B). Overall, families agreed: children of color,

should be able to see themselves represented because they're here; there are Black people here; there are Asian people; there are so many people here. Why do I not see that reflected in my spaces?... Because there are other kids just like them, that look like them, that are smart too. (Focus Group 1B)

What Families of Color Want

The families in this study expressed a collective desire for support and representation. They wanted quality education programs for their children without the "battle" (Focus Group 1B). Moreover, families welcomed open dialogue and made it clear that they want a seat at the table, "All you've got to do is talk to the people you want to serve because we'll tell you—hey, this is what I need; and then you can do it, and we can all be happy" (Focus Group 1B). More importantly, they expressed that they wanted these conversations to lead to "change" (Focus Group 1A).

Support and Community

The support families wanted included open communication and increased access to information. As one parent explained, "it seems really simple, if they could just talk to any of the actual population they're trying to serve. So, if you're not doing that, and it's not happening, it's because you're not actively trying to serve the population" (Focus Group 1B). Collectively, families wanted "open communications throughout the [school] district" (Focus Group 1A), and they wanted to feel supported by their community. Families shared ideas aimed at increasing communication and access to information, one of which involved community advocates and educators, "someone that can help to create a safe space for parents to be able to ask the

questions and to gather information and to actually connect” (Focus Group 1A). Through partnerships between the school and the local community, families hoped for greater access to gifted education programs (including related information to gifted education programs in their schools and communities) and an increase in options available to them *where they are*.

Families also wanted support in the form of parent communities. They explained that it was “hard to even find some people to connect with when you have an [advanced] child,” and they expressed their desire for a “support system” (Focus Group 1A). However, when family participants had found their place in a parent community, they shared experiences of empowerment: “I took her by the hand, and we were there” (Focus Group 1B), because “when you have a group of parents, they will fight for you too” (Focus Group 2). For these families, finding support and community with other parents was not just about camaraderie; it was about empowering them to persist through these challenges and fight for change.

Diversity and Representation

When asked what they wanted, families wanted programs with increased diversity where their children would feel seen and see themselves in others. For instance, some families talked about the general need for, “people of color in these groups” (Focus Group 1B), and in cases where school districts lack racially diverse school personnel, families wanted school personnel who are “culturally inclusive” at the very least (Focus Group 1B). Another parent emphasized the importance of having a racially diverse gifted education program and how it, “will help [their child] if they see someone who looks like them—people who look like them, you know what I mean. So, it’s just another way of saying, ‘Mom, I belong there’” (Focus Group 2). Families discussed the relationship between representation and their children feeling a sense of belonging and value in gifted education programs. As one parent explained, “... I want them to be in a

program that still sees the value in them and their exceptional aptitude... and enjoy that journey with them” (Focus Group 1B). Families also shared the importance of bringing (and retaining) gifted education programs to their communities, “we felt like we were empowering our own communities, sort of cause and effect, and [it’s] really important for older kids. Also, for younger kids to see themselves represented” (Focus Group 2). Moreover, families wanted their children to thrive in advanced learning programs that provided appropriate challenge, “I don’t want a ceiling on my child. I want him to not just feel okay, but I want him to thrive, and I want him to be challenged” (Focus Group 2). The various wants and desires expressed by the families in our study boiled down to this: equitable access to high quality gifted education programs where their children were seen and had the opportunity to realize their potential.

Overall, families were dissatisfied with current education services and advanced learning opportunities but expressed the importance of quality learning experiences for their children. Families reported advanced learning opportunities as inaccessible to them, and most were unfamiliar with gifted education programs and identification procedures in their school district. Moreover, families pointed to diverse representation as a critical facet of their child’s learning experiences, or at the minimum, they wanted teachers to practice social awareness and cultural sensitivity. Finally, the families of color in this study voiced their desire for advanced learning opportunities for their children, but they also wanted opportunities in environments that remove barriers (e.g., transportation), reflect diversity, and provide a sense of belonging for their children.

Discussion

Overall, themes described families’ experiences and perceptions as they related to their children’s academic experience and their access (or lack of) to enrichment and advanced

academic opportunities. More specifically, several themes revealed shared challenges and barriers related to enrichment and advanced academics as experienced by families of color. Based on these findings, to meaningfully progress in the field of gifted education, we must consider the voices of the families we serve. Under CRT, the knowledge and experiences of people of color are valued (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018). These families shared their experiences and challenges related to navigating an environment where whiteness is the norm (Owen, 2007). Moreover, the families' voices in this study shed light on the role common practices used in gifted education play to perpetuate whiteness as the norm and thus, perpetuate racial inequity (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018).

Wells and Plucker (2022) described an equity-minded frame as one that, “focuses this work on the goal of intersectional social justice for equitable advanced learning environments, during which we center the voices and lived experiences of students who have been marginalized” (p. 108). In this study, we centered the voices and lived experiences of families of color in the Seattle area. The voices from the families of FOCS left powerful impressions upon our RPP team. Themes, such as challenges, communication, and sense of belonging, that clearly emerged during the focus group interviews and analysis phase can all be explained through critical race and whiteness theories. What clearly emerged were *racial* challenges to access, *racial* conscious communication, a sense of *racial and cultural* belonging, and systematic *racial* barriers. These themes illuminated the experiences many families of color endure and their continued struggle with systems of oppression (Hylton, 2012). In this study, families were vulnerable in sharing their experiences when accessing, or *trying to access*, and navigating advanced learning opportunities for their children. Much of the experiences shared were stories of frustration and exhaustion, and their accounts indicated larger systemic issues that normalize

whiteness in American society (Chen, 2017; Owen, 2007). The message was quite clear: these families needed to see action and change.

Challenges to Access for Families of Color

When sharing their experiences, families reported the challenges they encountered when trying to access advanced learning opportunities for their children. Like Mun and colleagues' findings (2021), in our study, families agreed that they lacked access to information and referred to gifted education programs as the best kept secret. This coincides with whiteness as property under CRT (Barlow & Dunbar, 2010) and fuels the argument of gifted education as a present-day form of segregation (Barnes, 2022; Ford & King, 2014). Access to resources is connected to complex community networks that include relationships between families and schools (Yull et al., 2014). Not providing the same information to all families or participating in the act of gatekeeping information, places certain families at a disadvantage before they even begin.

Findings from focus group interviews revealed communication as another major area of inequity. This coincided with other studies that identified communication as a major barrier for families of color (Allen & White-Smith, 2017; Posey-Maddox & Haley-Lock, 2020). Communication related to gifted education assessment and services was also a primary issue for parents in a study conducted by Mun and colleagues (2021). Moreover, parents noted the lack of information and transparency and irregular communication as barriers to identification and access of gifted education services (Mun et al., 2021). In this study, focus group discussions on communication revealed that families of color perceived communication as nonexistent or as a tedious process in which they had to navigate. It is possible that families' school communities expected parents of color to engage with the school in ways that are like White, middle-class parents (Ford & King, 2014; Howard, 2018; Posey-Maddox & Haley-Lock, 2020; Yull et al.,

2018), thus reinforcing whiteness as largely invisible to White people yet a highly visible barrier for people of color (Owen, 2007). This also appeared to be related to families of color surveying and navigating the white space (Anderson, 2015). Family participants in this study not only addressed the absence of communication in some cases (Allen & White, 2017), but they also talked about how they were perceived as a person of color or immigrant (i.e., the intersection of race, linguistic background; Adair, 2015; Chapman & Bhopal, 2013; Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018) and the trickiness that accompanied conversations that occurred when they had to advocate for their children.

Challenges related to testing were prevalent across focus group interviews. Many families did not agree with the frequency of tests administered or the use of a test score to determine eligibility in advanced academic programs. They addressed additional concerns related to financial advantages and disadvantages (e.g., private pay testing). This pointed to the relationship between a competition-based system of achievement and racial inequity as defined by CRT (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018) and Makel's (2022) point on wealth gaps, "as long as resource access is connected to learning opportunities, wealth inequity will matter for learning" (p. 101). All in all, tests used for gifted identification were perceived as another point of contention or an additional hurdle for families of color in this study.

Families also voiced their concerns regarding racial bias in tests used to determine eligibility. Although predictive validity has been well established for intelligence tests (Erwin & Worrell, 2012), it is important to consider that many of these tests are still perceived as racially biased by many educational stakeholders. These concerns may be connected to other characteristics that can impact the quality of experiences or opportunities available to children of color (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018; Erwin & Worrell, 2012; Ford et al., 2016). Gifted

education researchers have cautioned against relying on a single measure and instead emphasized the need for multiple criteria as best practice for gifted identification (Johnsen, 2011; Lee et al., 2020; Worrell et al., 2019). It is possible that while gifted education scholars emphasize the use of multiple criteria as a best practice for gifted identification, other constituents (e.g., practitioners, parents, online communities like TestingMom.com) may continue to emphasize this single point of admission criteria, or tests, regardless of a school district's actual gifted education policy. As a result, for the families of color in our study, this reinforced whiteness as property, or the "absolute right to exclude" (Harris, 1995; Howard, 2018, p. 556), while also demonstrating the existing gap between research and practice and how this gap can perpetuate false beliefs and misinformation.

During focus group interviews, many families highlighted challenges related to time, finances, and transportation. They reported not having the time or the resources to navigate a system that was not made for them or did not feel welcoming to them. They shared challenges associated with lack of time, complexities of transportation in and around their community in Seattle and securing the funding to provide extra enrichment activities for their children. Many of the families worked full-time, some as single parents, and pointed out the tedious process of having to research or search for information related to advanced academic and enrichment programs. Within the CRT framework, the presence of "other identity markers," such as single parent households or socioeconomic background, had a clear impact on the families in our study and their access to advanced learning opportunities (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018, p. 122). Yet, universally, these families of color were interested in seeking the best programs for their children so that they may have better opportunities for their future growth and development. Family participants also requested that these programs accommodate families of color by making

them available to students in their home schools, in their communities, and with teachers and peers that looked like them.

Systemic Issues and Barriers for Families of Color

When asked about advanced academic programming, the families of color in this study shared their experiences navigating white spaces. According to Anderson (2015),

when present in the white space, Blacks reflexively note the proportion of Whites to Blacks, or may look around for other Blacks with whom to commune if not bond, and then may adjust their comfort level accordingly; when judging a setting as too white, they can feel uneasy and consider it to be informally ‘off limits.’ (p. 10)

This stems back to *Brown v. Board of Education* (1954), where the act of desegregation meant closing black schools as opposed to white schools which sent the message that black schools were not good enough for White children (Pasque et al., 2022); thus, illustrating historical patterns of racial oppression still at work today (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018). Families’ quotes reflected the uneasiness and discomfort for both the parents and the child participating in advanced academic programs.

Families shared instances of racism, bias, and microaggression experienced by themselves and their children. They also spoke of the harmful narratives that reinforced the notion that people of color are inferior (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018) which also aligned with Anderson’s (2015) statement, “For there are always people who are ready and able to discourage the Black person or to discredit him or her through association with the iconic ghetto, at times for their own self-esteem or advancement” (p. 17). Family participants reported school professionals that showed bias and prejudice through explicit behaviors, an experience that is all too common for families of color (Reynolds, 2010; Romero et al., 2015). Families also voiced

implicit behaviors that prevented their access to or discouraged continued enrollment in advanced and enrichment opportunities for their children. Similar experiences have been highlighted by parents in other studies (Allen & White-Smith, 2017; Gatwiri & Anderson, 2020; Yull et al., 2014). Families in our study shared an overwhelming lack of sense of belonging in gifted education programs as demonstrated by nuanced reasons related to issues of recruitment and retainment of students of color in gifted education, an issue pointed out by other researchers (Ecker-Lyster & Niileksela, 2017; Ford & Whiting, 2008; Worrell & Dixson, 2018).

Families' accounts should serve as a wake-up call for educational researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. Not only were procedures perceived as barriers to access, especially the emphasis on testing, but the differential treatment of individuals based on their race and culture—intentional or not—was evident and must be addressed. Prioritizing cultural awareness and responsiveness in ongoing professional learning opportunities and pre-service programs (Ford & Whiting, 2008; Grissom & Redding, 2016) is an essential step toward progress. In line with CRT, existing practices must be interrogated, and practices that value the knowledge and experiences of people of color should be implemented. We would also argue that attention and resources should be shifted from identification to the nature and content of gifted education programs. Restructuring gifted education services to consider and support individual learning needs, particularly underrepresented students, is a good place to start.

What Families of Color Want

Overall, the families in this study wanted support and community as well as increased diversity and representation in advanced academic and enrichment programs. For these families, support and community not only pointed to their desire for open communication and increased access to information, but the structural entitlements and white spaces families of color are

forced to navigate in their attempts to access advanced opportunities for their children (Anderson, 2015; Whiting, 2022). The families in our study also proposed ideas aimed at meeting this need such as community advocates, partnerships between schools and the local community, and more options for advanced academic programs available to them where they are (e.g., neighborhood schools, local community centers). Limiting advanced academic programs to a particular school in a district and bussing kids out of their neighborhoods is a prime example of policies and practices that limit equitable access and perpetuate whiteness as the norm (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018). Parent communities were also a desired area of support by family participants. In a study on parent mentor groups, parents of color closely bonded with one another during the first week of training. Researchers concluded that this reflected the type of connection parents desired but had previously lacked the opportunities needed to build these types of relationships (Yull et al., 2018). The families of color in this study shared that it was difficult to connect with people, but they still wanted a support system. They also shared feelings of empowerment when they did find those connections within their parent community. Similarly, in the study conducted by Yull and colleagues (2018), parents of color shared feelings of empowerment, increased confidence, and deep connection through their participation in the parent mentor program.

Also notable was family participants' shared desire for increased diversity in school personnel and student peers in the gifted education program. Increased diversity is necessary to counter the harmful narrative that people of color are inferior (Dixson & Rousseau-Anderson, 2018). In an interview study, Black adults reflected on their time as students in a diverse gifted education program that "embraced black academic excellence" (Sewell & Goings, 2019, p. 26). Moreover, Sewell and Goings found that participants had an easy transition in elementary gifted

education programs due to racial diversity but experienced a difficult transition at middle and high school due to less diverse student populations or having to attend a school outside of their neighborhood school. Having a supportive community during their transition to a less diverse high school was integral to their success (Sewell & Goings, 2019). The families of color in this study also emphasized the connection between diverse representation and a sense of belonging. Family participants were clear that it was important for their children to be seen by others and see themselves in others. Sense of belonging is an important psychosocial factor in learning (Barbieri-Ariezaga & Miller-Cotto, 2021; Gummadam et al., 2015). Students are more willing to take intellectual risks and experience academic and psychological benefits when they feel a sense of belonging (Booker, 2016; Brooms, 2019). The families in this study believed that increasing access to gifted education programs in their own communities could mitigate some of the issues associated with the lack of diverse representation.

Conclusions, Limitations, and Future Research

This study illuminated only the tip of the iceberg of reasons why children of color may not participate in advanced learning opportunities, even when they have access. Although research on parent perspectives on equity issues in gifted education is lacking (Mun et al., 2021), researchers outside the field of gifted education have conducted studies with families of color regarding their roles and experiences in the education system. Many of the themes that emerged from the parent voices in this study echoed the experiences of parents of color in other areas of education (Adair, 2015; Allen & White-Smith, 2017; Chapman & Bhopal, 2013; Yull et al., 2014; Yull et al., 2018) and gifted education (Mun et al., 2021). A deeper understanding of the sociology of race and ethnicity and theoretical lenses that explore whiteness and white spaces is needed for the field of gifted education to better comprehend the complex issues related to

equity, access, and advanced programming. In addition, more equity-focused studies using the research-practice partnership (RPP) framework would broaden the scope of understanding of underrepresentation in our field.

The families of color in this study wanted school personnel who are culturally inclusive. From a practical standpoint, it is imperative that school leaders, teachers, and other personnel engage in multicultural awareness and culturally responsive training. Such efforts should not be viewed as optional training but as a professional responsibility:

The professional duty of culturally competent leaders stems from their will (Hilliard, 1991) to respond in an ethical manner to the students and families they serve and to act through reflective practice (Schön, 1983) as a way to carry out their professional duty. (Mun, Ezzani, et al., 2020, p. 113)

In a systematic review on culturally relevant leadership, the Arkansas Evaluation Initiative (AEI; Cotabish & Robinson, 2012) and the Young Scholars Model (Horn, 2015) were promising models of professional development in the areas of culturally responsive training in gifted education (Mun, Ezzani, et al., 2020). Future studies should consider adopting a RPP framework to build cultural competencies, using the AEI or the Young Scholars Model, and relationships with the school system and their local community.

School systems must also incorporate intentional work to engage families of color and provide them with a safe environment as part of the school community, particularly for communities that are predominately white. Yull and colleagues (2014) cautioned that power structures in communities that are predominantly one race need targeted attention and exhort endeavors that actively engage diverse families. However, intentional outreach to families of color related to gifted and advanced learning opportunities is still lacking (Ford & Whiting,

2007). Involving families as partners in gifted education programs is important in providing adequate support for students of color (Mun, Ezzani, et al., 2020). School personnel should consider using a combination of traditional and nontraditional family engagement models because of its effectiveness in encouraging parental involvement (Arias & Morillo-Campbell, 2008; Tarasawa & Waggoner, 2015). For example, schools can use multiple forms of communication (written and spoken), implement community outreach programs to better connect with families, and present a variety of participation opportunities that are sensitive to parents' work schedules (Tarasawa & Waggoner, 2015). The parent mentor program used by Yull and colleagues (2018) also provides a promising model for practitioners and researchers that can be adapted for implementation in gifted education programs and used to improve parent-school relationships and increase parent engagement.

This is a small study with limitations, both visible and invisible. We collected the data as White researchers; therefore, it is likely that families were navigating an additional white space, and some may have held back when sharing their experiences. Additionally, it is important to acknowledge that as White female researchers, our understanding of the world is characterized by our whiteness which may have impacted some families' willingness to openly share their experiences (Owen, 2007). Due to the locality of this research-practice partnership, the focus was on a specific community; therefore, it is important to acknowledge the limitations associated with the small number of participants and the locale of the study. Because gifted education varies by state, and even more so at the local level, it is important to acknowledge that the findings of this study are not generalizable to other contexts and populations. Although emerging themes did mirror some of those from other qualitative studies with families of color, we should not assume that barriers to advanced learning opportunities are similar across communities. Either way, what

these families had to say is important, and it is likely that other families of color hold similar experiences related to advanced academic programs. The experiences shared by the families in this study should serve as a call to action with intentional work around dismantling white spaces in educational contexts. We advocate for inclusive environments and individualized educational services that challenge and enrich students from all races, ethnicities, and income levels.

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Appendix

Exploring How Families of Color Experience Advanced Learning Opportunities

Interview Protocol

Script: First, I'd like to start by thanking each of you for your willingness to come in today and share your perspective and experiences with the group. I'd also like to tell you a little about myself and provide a little more background about our study and what we hope to accomplish through these focus group interviews. My name is _____, and I am a researcher with the Robinson Center for Young Scholars at the University of Washington (UWRC). The UWRC provides both enrichment programs and advanced learning opportunities through accelerated early entrance to the University of Washington. More on these opportunities can be found in your swag bag.

For context, advanced learning experiences are typically designed to academically challenge children who are working above their grade level peers in a school setting (e.g., gifted education programs, highly capable programs, advanced placement courses, grade skipping or acceleration). Enrichment experiences are typically designed to engage children in specific interest areas that nurture their excitement in learning and lead them to pursue specific topics in greater depth (e.g., going to museums, science center, enrichment classes, art and music lessons, or dance classes).

Historically, researchers have shown that children of color have experienced (and continue to experience) limited access to these types of learning opportunities. We are interested in learning more about you and your family's experiences related to advanced academic and enrichment learning opportunities as well as any challenges and barriers your family may have encountered when trying to access these learning opportunities for your children. Our aim is to understand these experiences and challenges from the individuals that are most impacted: families of color. We hope that our study will shed light on this issue and provide additional insight so that we can work together to come up with solutions that work for families of color.

We would like to record this interview; no names will be recorded or released in any of our publications. Recording the focus group interview only helps us to accurately remember what was shared so that we can better report our findings. Do we have your permission to record this interview? Remember, you are not obligated to answer any question that may cause you to feel uncomfortable, and you can withdraw your consent to participate at any time.

Questions

1. Background Information – Participants

Prompts:

- Can you tell us a little about yourselves? (how long have you lived in the Seattle area, how many members make up your family, how old are your children)

2. Background Knowledge – Highly Capable Programs

Prompts:

- Can you describe what you know about advanced and enrichment learning opportunities in your child's school or school district?
- Can you share what you know about enrichment and advanced learning opportunities offered outside of your child's school or school district? (For example, do you know of any community organizations in your area that offer these types of learning opportunities?)
- Please tell us about any of these opportunities that your children have been involved in (enrichment, advanced learning).

3. Perceived Barriers and Challenges for Families of Color Seattle

Prompts:

- What do you perceive as barriers or challenges for your child to access advanced learning opportunities offered by their school?
- What do you perceive as barriers or challenges for your child to access enrichment opportunities offered by their school?
- What do you perceive as barriers or challenges for your child to access these types of learning opportunities that are offered outside of their school?
- Can you tell us about a specific event or barrier experienced by your child and/or family? (this can be something that happened in your child's classroom or school or a program offered outside of the school district; it can also be something more logistical, like transportation, that prevented your child from participating)
- Do you know of any barriers experienced by other families of color?
- Do you have any advice for individuals trying to remove barriers and increase access to advanced and enriched learning opportunities for children of color?

4. Partnership with the UWRC

Prompts:

- What types of programs/classes would you bring your child to if offered by the UWRC?
- How can the UWRC better meet your family's needs when offering our programs in the future?